

A Review Study On Neutrosophic Groups and Their Generalizations

Rozina Ali

Independent Researcher, Cairo, Egypt, e-mail: rozvyy123@gmail.com

Abstract: This paper introduces a review study on the concept of neutrosophic groups, and n-refined neutrosophic groups. Also, it provides the reader a wide background in on important concepts and researches in some related topics and structures.

Key words: Neutrosophic group, refined neutrosophic group, n-refined neutrosophic group, AH-substructure, AH-solvable.

1. Introduction

Neutrosophy is a philosophical concept founded by Smarandache to generalize the fuzzy logic [1,32]. Neutrosophic sets were very applicative in many areas of science such as topology [2,27,60,61,63], decision making [21,35], applied mathematics [3,4,20,25,28,57,64], and pure mathematics [9,10,19,39,43,44,47,50,51,52].

Neutrosophic sets were used in the study of algebraic structures such as modules [6], rings [12], groups [13], and matrices [6,53,62]. In the literature, we find three interesting generalizations of neutrosophic sets, where refined neutrosophic sets [13] n-refined neutrosophic sets [15,50], and n-cyclic refined neutrosophic sets [31]. These kinds lead us to many interesting generalizations of classical algebraic structures such as n-refined neutrosophic modules [5], n-refined spaces and matrices [8,46,54], refined neutrosophic ring [23,48,49], and n-cyclic refined neutrosophic modules [31].

In this work, we give the interested reader a good review to the neutrosophic group theory and elementary concepts and properties in this field of algebraic structures.

2. Neutrosophic groups and some generalizations

Definition 2.1:

Let $(G,*)$ be a group. Then the neutrosophic group is generated by G and I under $*$ denoted by $N(G)=\langle G \cup I, * \rangle$.

I is called the indeterminate (neutrosophic element) with the property $I^2 = I$.

Definition 2.2:

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group and H be a neutrosophic subgroup, i.e., (H contains a proper subgroup of G). Then H is a neutrosophic normal subgroup of $N(G)$ if $xH = Hx$ for all $x \in N(G)$.

Definition 2.3:

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group. Then the center of $N(G)$ is denoted by $C(N(G))$, and defined

$$C(N(G)) = \{x \in N(G); xy = yx \forall y \in N(G)\}$$

Definition 2.4:

Let $N(G), N(H)$ be two neutrosophic groups, then $N(G) \times N(H) = \{(g, h); g \in N(G), h \in N(H)\}$.

Definition 2.5:

Let $N(G), N(H)$ be two neutrosophic groups and $\varphi: N(G) \rightarrow N(H)$ is called a neutrosophic homomorphism if it is a homomorphism between G, H and $\varphi(I) = I'$.

Where I' is the neutrosophic element of $N(H)$.

If φ is a correspondence one-to-one it is called a neutrosophic isomorphism.

Example 2.6:

Let $Z_7 = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 6\}$ be the group of integers under addition modulo 7. $N(G) = \{\langle Z_7 \cup I \rangle, '+' \text{ modulo } 7\}$ is a neutrosophic group which is in fact a group. For $N(G) = \{a + bI; a, b \in Z_7\}$ is a group under '+' modulo 7. Thus this neutrosophic group is also a group.

Theorem 2.7:

Let $(G, *)$ be a group, $N(G) = \{\langle G \cup I \rangle, *\}$ be the neutrosophic group. Then

$N(G)$ in general is not a group.
 $N(G)$ always contains a group.

Example 2.8:

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group generated by (Z_7^*, \cdot) , given by $N(G) = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, I, 2I, 3I, 4I, 5I, 6I\}$ be a neutrosophic group under multiplication modulo 7.

$H = \{1, 6, I, 6I\}$ is a neutrosophic subgroup of $N(G)$. For $x \in N(G)$, $xH = Hx$, so H is normal in $N(G)$.

Definition 2.9:

Let $(G, *)$ be a group, we define the corresponding n -refined neutrosophic group $N_n(G)$ as follows:

$$N_n(G) = (\langle G \cup \{I_1, \dots, I_n\} \rangle, *) = \{(a_0, a_1 I_1, \dots, a_n I_n); a_i \in G\}$$

It is easy to see that $N_n(G)$ is closed under $*$, and it is a semigroup but not a group since I_i has no inverse with respect to $*$ in general.

Remark 2.10:

If $(G, +)$ is an additive abelian group, then addition on $N_n(G)$ can be described as follows:

Consider $x = (a_0, a_1 I_1, \dots, a_n I_n), y = (b_0, b_1 I_1, \dots, b_n I_n)$, we have

. In this case $(N_n(G), +)$ is a classical abelian group. $x + y = (a_0 + b_0, [a_1 + b_1]I_1, \dots, [a_n + b_n]I_n)$

The identity element is $(0, 0, \dots, 0)$.

It is easy to see that $N_n(G) \cong G \times G \times \dots \times G$ ($n + 1$ times) in the case of abelian additive group G .

Remark 2.11:

If G is a multiplicative group, then group product on $N_n(G)$ can be described as follows:

Consider $x = (a_0, a_1I_1, \dots, a_nI_n), y = (b_0, b_1I_1, \dots, b_nI_n)$, we have

$$xy = (t_0, t_1, \dots, t_n); t_s = \prod_{i,j=0}^n (a_i b_j) I_i I_j; I_0 = e_G \text{ and } I_i I_j = I_s$$

The identity element is $(e_G, e_G I_1, \dots, e_G I_n)$.

In this case $N_n(G)$ is not isomorphic to the direct product of $n+1$ copies of G , since it is not a classical group in this case.

The binary operation between the sub-indeterminacies is $I_i \cdot I_j = I_{\min(i,j)}$.

Remark: If $n = 2$, we get the concept of refined neutrosophic group.

Example 2.12:

Let $G = Z_2$ be the additive group of integers modulo 2, the corresponding 2-refined neutrosophic group is $N_2(G) = \{(0,0,0), (1,0,0), (0, I_1, 0), (0,0, I_2), (1, I_1, 0), (1,0, I_2), (0, I_1, I_2), (1, I_1, I_2)\}$.

$$(1,0, I_2) + (1, I_1, I_2) = (0, I_1, 0)$$

Example 2.13:

Let $G = S_3 = \{f_0 = I, f_1, f_2, f_3, f_4, f_5\}$ be the non abelian symmetric group of order 6, the corresponding 2-refined neutrosophic group is $N_2(G) = \{(a, bI_1, cI_2); a, b, c \in G\}$.

We clarify the product on $N_2(G)$ as follows:

Consider $x = (f_1, f_2I_1, f_0I_2), y = (f_2, f_1I_1, f_4I_2)$, we have

$$xy = (f_1f_2, [(f_1f_1)(f_2f_2)(f_2f_1)(f_2f_4)(f_0f_1)]I_1, [(f_1f_4)(f_0f_2)(f_0f_4)]I_2)$$

Definition 2.14:

(a) Let $N_n(G)$ be an n -refined neutrosophic group. It is called abelian if $x * y = y * x$ for all $x, y \in N_n(G)$.

(b) The subset $Z(N_n(G)) = \{y \in N_n(G); y * x = x * y \text{ for all } x \in N_n(G)\}$ is called n -refined neutrosophic center.

Theorem 2.15:

Let $N_n(G)$ be an n -refined neutrosophic group. Then

- (a) If G is abelian, $N_n(G)$ is abelian.
- (b) $N_n(G)$ is abelian if and only if $N_n(G) = Z(N_n(G))$.

Definition 2.16:

Let $N_n(G)$ be an n -refined neutrosophic group, H be a nonempty subset of $N_n(G)$, we say that H is an n -refined neutrosophic subgroup if H contains a subgroup of G .

Example 2.17:

Let $G = Z_2$ be the additive group of integers modulo 2, the corresponding 3-refined neutrosophic group is $N_3(G)$. The set $H = \{(0,0,0), (1,0,0), (1, I_1, 0), (1,0, I_2)\}$ is an n-refined neutrosophic subgroup of $N_3(G)$, since it contains $G = \{0,1\}$ which is a subgroup of G .

By previous example, we can see that Lagrange's theorem is not true in general in the case of finite n-refined neutrosophic group.

Definition 2.18:

Let $N_n(G)$ be an n-refined neutrosophic group, we denote to the number of elements in $N_n(G)$ by

$O(N_n(G))$. If $N_n(G)$ is finite, then $O(N_n(G)) = m$, elsewhere $O(N_n(G)) = \infty$.

$O(N_n(G))$ is called the order of n-refined neutrosophic group $N_n(G)$.

Theorem 2.19:

Let G be a finite group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group. Then if $O(G) = m$, we have $O(N_n(G)) = m^{n+1}$.

Proof:

Since $N_n(G) = (\langle G \cup \{I_1, \dots, I_n\} \rangle, *) = \{(a_0, a_1 I_1, \dots, a_n I_n); a_i \in G\}$, we find that

$$O(N_n(G)) = O(G) \times O(G) \times \dots \times O(G) (n + 1 \text{ times}) = m^{n+1}$$

Definition 2.20:

Let $N_n(G), N_n(K)$ be two n-refined neutrosophic groups, $f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K)$ be a well defined map, we say that f is an n-refined neutrosophic homomorphism if:

(a) $f(xy) = f(x)f(y)$ for all $x, y \in N_n(G)$.

(b) $f(e_G, e_G, \dots, I_k, e_G, \dots, e_G) = (e_G, e_G, \dots, I_k, e_G, \dots, e_G)$.

Example 2.21:

Let $G = Z, K = Z_4, f: N_2(G) \rightarrow N_2(K); f(x, yI_1, zI_2) = ((x \bmod 4), (y \bmod 4)I_1, (z \bmod 4)I_2)$

, where $x, y, z \in Z$.

Let $m = (x, yI_1, zI_2), n = (a, bI_1, cI_2)$ be two arbitrary elements in $N_2(G)$, it is clear that

$$f(m + n) = f(m) + f(n)$$

. Thus f is an n-refined $f(I_1) = f(0, 1, 0, I_2) = (0, I_1, 0), f(I_2) = f(0, 0, 1, I_2) = (0, 0, I_2)$ neutrosophic homomorphism.

Definition 2.22:

Let $N_n(G), N_n(K)$ be two n-refined neutrosophic groups, $f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K)$ be an n-refined neutrosophic homomorphism, we define:

(a) $\text{Ker}(f) = \{x \in N_n(G); f(x) = e_{N_n(K)}\}$.

(b) $Im(f) = \{y \in N_n(K); \exists x \in N_n(G): f(x) = y\}$.

Theorem 2.23:

Let $N_n(G), N_n(K)$ be two n-refined neutrosophic groups, $f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K)$ be an n-refined neutrosophic homomorphism, we have:

(a) $Ker(f)$ is an n-refined neutrosophic subgroup of $N_n(G)$.

(b) $Im(f)$ is an n-refined neutrosophic subgroup of $N_n(K)$.

Proof:

(a) Since the restriction f_G of f is a homomorphism between

G and K , its kernel $Ker(f_G)$ will be a subset of $Ker(f)$, i.e $Ker(f)$ contains a subgroup of G , hence it is an n-refined neutrosophic subgroup according to Definition 3.8.

(b) The proof is similar to (a).

Example 2.24:

Let $G = Z, K = Z_4, f: N_2(G) \rightarrow N_2(K); f(x, yI_1, zI_2) = ((x \bmod 4), (y \bmod 4)I_1, (z \bmod 4)I_2)$

, where $x, y, z \in Z$.

, which is a 2-refined neutrosophic subgroup, $Ker(f) = (4Z, 4ZI_1, 4ZI_2) = \{4x, 4yI_1, 4zI_2; x, y, z \in Z\}$ since it contains $L = 4Z$.

, which is a 2-refined subgroup, since it contains $S = Z_4. Im(f) = \{(a, bI_1, cI_2); a, b, c \in Z_4\} = N_2(K)$

Definition 2.25:

Let $N_n(G), N_n(K)$ be two n-refined neutrosophic groups, $f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K)$ be an n-refined neutrosophic homomorphism, we call it an n-refined neutrosophic isomorphism if it is bijective.

Example 2.26:

Let $G = Z$ be the group of integers with normal addition, $N_3(G) = \{(a, bI_1, cI_2, dI_3); a, b, c, d \in Z\}$ be its corresponding 3-refined neutrosophic group. We define

, it is clear that f is a bijective n-refined $f: N_3(G) \rightarrow N_3(G); f(a, bI_1, cI_2, dI_3) = (-a, bI_1, cI_2, dI_3)$ neutrosophic homomorphism, thus it is an n-refined neutrosophic isomorphism.

3. Special Substructures of Neutrosophic groups

Definition 3.1 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group and K be a subset of $N(G)$, we say that K is an AH-subgroup if $K=H \cup T$ such that H is a subgroup of G and T is a subgroup of GI .

Example 3.2 :

Let $G = Z_4$, then $K=\{0, 2, I\}$ is an AH-subgroup of $N(G)$ because $\{0, 2\}$ is a subgroup of G and $\{I\}$ is a subgroup of the pure neutrosophic group GI under the operation defined in Theorem 3.3.

Definition 3.3 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group, K be an AH-subgroup, we say that K is AHS-subgroup if $T \cong H$.

Definition 3.4 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group, K be an AH-subgroup we say that K is an AH-normal subgroup if H is normal in G and T is normal in GI .

Definition 3.5 :

(a) Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group and K be an AHS-subgroup, we say that K is an AHS-normal subgroup if it is AH-normal.

Definition 3.6 :

Let $N(G)$, $N(H)$ be two neutrosophic groups and $f_G: G \rightarrow H$ be a homomorphism, we define the corresponding AHS-homomorphism as follows:

$$f: N(G) \rightarrow N(H); f(x + yI) = f_G(x) + f_G(y)I$$

We define $AH - Ker(f) = Ker(f_G) \cup Ker(f_{GI})$. It is easy to see that $Ker f_G \cong Ker f_{GI}$, so that $AH - Ker(f)$ is an AHS-subgroup of $N(G)$.

We can understand the AH-Kernel as a union, $AH - ker(f) = Ker f_G \cup Ker f_{GI}$.

Theorem 3.7 :

Let f be an AHS-homomorphism between $N(G)$ and $N(H)$. We have

- (a) $AH - Ker(f)$ is an AHS-normal subgroup of $N(G)$.
- (b) $N(G)/AH - Ker(f) \cong f_G(G) \cup f_G(G)I$. (The isomorphism here is taken by the concept of AHS-isomorphism).

The quotient in (b) is taken as AH-quotient.

Proof :

- (a) Since $Ker(f_G)$ and $Ker(f_{GI})$ are normal in G , GI respectively, $AH - Ker(f)$ is AHS-normal.
- (b) We have $G/Ker f_G \cong f_G(G)$ and $GI/Ker f_{GI} \cong f_{GI}(GI)$,

$$f(N(G)) = f(G) \cup f(GI) \cong G/Ker(f_G) \cup GI/Ker(f_{GI}) = N(G)/AH - Ker(f).$$

(b) Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group, $K = K_1 \cup K_2$, $S = S_1 \cup S_2$ be two AH-subgroups. The intersection is defined as $K \cap S = (K_1 \cap S_1) \cup (K_2 \cap S_2)$.

Theorem 3.8 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group, then

- (a) If K, S are two AH-subgroups, $K \cap S$ is AH-subgroup.
- (b) If K, S are two AHS-subgroups, $K \cap S$ is AHS-subgroup.
- (c) If K, S are two AH-normal subgroups, $K \cap S$ is AH-normal subgroup.
- (d) If K, S are two AHS-normal subgroups, $K \cap S$ is AHS-normal subgroup.

Proof :

(a) Suppose that $K = K_1 \cup K_2$, $S = S_1 \cup S_2$, then $K \cap S = (K_1 \cap S_1) \cup (K_2 \cap S_2)$ is an AH-subgroup, because

is a subgroup of G and $K_2 \cap S_2$ is a subgroup of GI . $K_1 \cap S_1$

(b) The proof holds directly from (a).

(c) If K_1, S_1 are normal subgroups of G and K_2, S_2 are normal in GI , then $K_2 \cap S_2$ is normal in GI and $K_1 \cap S_1$ is normal in G , thus $K \cap S = (K_1 \cap S_1) \cup (K_2 \cap S_2)$ is AH-normal subgroup.

(d) It holds from (c).

Definition 3.9 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic subgroup with two AH-subgroups $K=K_1 \cup K_2$, $S=S_1 \cup S_2$.

We define $KS = K_1S_1 \cup K_2S_2$.

Theorem 3.10 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic subgroup with two AH-normal subgroups $K=K_1 \cup K_2$, $S=S_1 \cup S_2$, then KS is an AH-normal subgroup.

Proof :

Since K_1S_1 is normal subgroup of G and K_2S_2 is normal in GI . The proof is complete.

Definition 3.11:

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic subgroup with an AH-normal subgroup $K=K_1 \cup K_2$. We define the AH-Quotient $N(G)/K = G/K_1 \cup GI/K_2$.

If K is an AHS-normal subgroup, then $N(G)/K$ is called AHS-Quotient.

The AHS-Quotient $N(G)/K$ must be understood as $G/K_1 \cup (G/K_1)I$ because $K_1 \cong K_2$.

Remark 3.12 :

If $K=K_1 \cup K_2$ and $S=S_1 \cup S_2$ are two AH-subgroups, we say that $K \cong S$ if and only if $K_1 \cong S_1$ and $K_2 \cong S_2$.

Theorem 3.13 :

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group with an AH-normal subgroup K . Then

(a) If $N(G)$ is abelian, then $N(G)/K$ is abelian.

(b) If K is an AHS-normal subgroup, and $xK = yK$ for $x, y \in G$, then $xy^{-1} \in K_1$. Also, if $y = zI \in GI$, then $xz^{-1} \in K_1$.

(c) If G is finite and K is AHS-subgroup, $o(K)$ will divide $o(N(G))$.

Proof :

(a) It can be proved as the classical case.

(b) Suppose that $y \in G$, then by the proposition we have $xK_1 \cup xIK_2 = yK_1 \cup yIK_2$, so $xK_1 = yK_1$, thus $xy^{-1} \in K_1$.

Now if $y = zI \in GI$, then $xK_1 \cup xIK_2 = zK_1 \cup zIK_2$, hence $xK_1 = zK_1$, thus $xz^{-1} \in K_1$.

(c) It holds directly from Lagrange's theorem.

Example 3.14 :

Let $G = Z_6$ be the group of integers modulo 6 with respect to addition, we have $\{0, 2, 4, I, 3+I\}$ is an AH-normal subgroup, because $\{0,2,4\}$ is normal in G and $\{I, 3+I\}$ is normal in GI . The corresponding AH-quotient is

$\{ 1+\{ 0, 2, 4 \} , \{ 0, 2, 4 \} , \{I, 3+I\} , (1+I)+\{I, 3+I\} , (2+I)+\{I, 3+I\} \}$.

$\{0, 3, I, 3+I\}$ is an AHS-normal subgroup of $N(G)$ and the related AHS-quotient is

$\{ \{0,3\} , 1+\{0,3\} , 2+\{0,3\} , \{I, 3+I\} , (1+I)+\{I, 3+I\} , (2+I)+\{I, 3+I\} \}$.

Definition 3.15:

Let $N(G)$ be a neutrosophic group, $N(H) = T \cup S; T \leq G, S \leq GI$ be an AH-subgroup, we say

- (a) $N(H)$ is an AH-solvable subgroup if T, S are solvable.
- (b) $N(H)$ is an AH-nilpotent subgroup if T, S are nilpotent.
- (c) $N(H)$ is an AH-abelian subgroup if T, S are abelian.
- (d) $N(H)$ is an AH-cyclic subgroup if T, S are cyclic.

Example 3.16:

Let $G = S_3, T = \langle (1\ 2) \rangle, S = \langle (1\ 2\ 3) \rangle$ be two subgroups of G , we have

(a) $SI = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} I, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix} I \right\}$ is a subgroup of GI .

(b) $N(H) = T \cup S = \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 1 & 3 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 2 & 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix} I, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 1 & 2 \end{pmatrix} I, \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \end{pmatrix} I \right\}$ is an AH-subgroup of $N(G)$.

- (c) $N(H)$ is AH-cyclic and AH-abelian subgroup, since T, S are cyclic and abelian.
- (d) $N(H)$ is AH-Nilpotent and AH-solvable, since T, S are nilpotent and solvable.

Definition 3.17:

Let G be any group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group, $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n); H_i \leq G$ be an AH-subgroup of $N_n(G)$. We say

- (a) $N_n(H)$ is AH-normal subgroup if H_i is normal for all i .
- (b) $N_n(H)$ is AH-nilpotent subgroup if H_i is nilpotent for all i .
- (c) $N_n(H)$ is AH-solvable subgroup if H_i is solvable for all i .
- (d) $N_n(H)$ is AH-meta abelian subgroup if H_i is meta abelian for all i .

(e) $N_n(H)$ is AH-simple subgroup if H_i is simple for all i .

Example 3.18:

Consider the symmetric group of order 6 ($G = S_3$), it has one normal subgroup $H \cong Z_3$, and three 2-Sylow subgroups $K \cong S \cong L \cong Z_2$.

Let $N_2(G)$ be the corresponding 2-refined neutrosophic group, we have

- (a) $M_1 = (K, KI_1, HI_2)$ is an AH-subgroup of $N_2(G)$.
- (b) M_1 is an AH-nilpotent/AH-solvable, since K,H are nilpotent, and solvable subgroups of G.
- (c) M_1 is an AH-simple, since K,H are simple.
- (d) M_1 is not an AH-normal, since K is not normal.
- (e) M_1 is an AH-meta abelian, since H,K are meta abelian subgroups.

Remark 3.19:

If G is an additive abelian group, then any AH-subgroup is a classical subgroup. This is because $N_n(G)$ is a classical group and isomorphic to the direct product of G with itself (n+1 times).

Definition 3.20:

Let G,K be any two groups, $N_n(G), N_n(K)$ be their corresponding n-refined neutrosophic groups,

$0 \leq i \leq n$ be a classical homomorphism for all i . We say $f_i: G \rightarrow K$

- (a) $f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K); f(a_0, a_1I_1, \dots, a_nI_n) = (f_0(a_0), f_1(a_1)I_1, \dots, f_n(a_n)I_n)$ is an AH-homomorphism.
- (b) If $f_i: G \rightarrow K$ is an isomorphism for all i , then $f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K)$ is called an AH-isomorphism.
- (c) If $f_i = f_j; i \neq j$, then $f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K)$ is called an AHS-homomorphism.
- (d) The AH-kernel is defined as follows: $AH - Ker(f) = (Ker(f_0), Ker(f_1)I_1, \dots, Ker(f_n)I_n)$.
- (e) The AH-image is defined as: $AH - Im(f) = (f_0(G), f_1(G)I_1, \dots, f_n(G)I_n)$.

We denote to the AH-homomorphism $: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K); f(a_0, a_1I_1, \dots, a_nI_n) = (f_0(a_0), f_1(a_1)I_1, \dots, f_n(a_n)I_n)$ by

$$f = (f_0, f_1I_1, \dots, f_nI_n)$$

Definition 3.21:

Let G be any group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group,

be any two AH-subgroups of $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n), N(K) = (K_0, K_1I_1, \dots, K_nI_n); H_i, K_i \leq N_n(G)$.

- (a) We define the intersection as follows: $N_n(H) \cap N_n(K) = (H_0 \cap K_0, (H_1 \cap K_1)I_1, \dots, (H_n \cap K_n)I_n)$.
- (b) We define the product as follows: $N_n(H) \cdot N_n(K) = (H_0 \cdot K_0, (H_1 \cdot K_1)I_1, \dots, (H_n \cdot K_n)I_n)$.

(c) We define the direct product as follows: $N_n(H) \times N_n(K) = (H_0 \times K_0, (H_1 \times K_1)I_1, \dots, (H_n \times K_n)I_n)$.

Example 3.22:

Consider the symmetric group of order 6 ($G = S_3$), it has one normal subgroup $H \cong Z_3$, and three 2-Sylow subgroups $K \cong S \cong L \cong Z_2$.

Let $N_2(G)$ be the corresponding 2-refined neutrosophic group, $M_1 = (K, KI_1, HI_2)$, $M_2 = (H, KI_1, KI_2)$ be two AH-subgroups of $N_2(G)$, we have

(a) $M_1 \cap M_2 = (\{e\}, KI_1, \{e\}I_2)$, which is an AH-subgroup of $N_2(G)$.

(b) $M_1 \cdot M_2 = (KH, KKI_1, HKI_2) = (G, KI_1, GI_2)$.

Example 3.23:

Let $G = (Z, +)$, $K = (Z_6, +)$ be two groups, $N_2(G)$, $N_2(K)$ be the corresponding 2-refined neutrosophic groups, we have

(a) $f_0: G \rightarrow K; f_0(a) = a \text{ mod } 6, f_1: G \rightarrow K; f_1(a) = 2a \text{ mod } 6$ are two classical homomorphisms.

(b) $f: N_2(G) \rightarrow N_2(K); f(a_0, a_1I_1, a_2I_2) = (f_0(a_0), f_0(a_1)I_1, f_1(a_2)I_2) = (a_0 \text{ mod } 6, a_1 \text{ mod } 6 I_1, 2a_2 \text{ mod } 6 I_2)$ is an AH-homomorphism.

(c) $AH - Ker(f) = (Ker(f_0), Ker(f_0)I_1, Ker(f_1)I_2) = (6Z, 6ZI_1, 3ZI_2)$.

(d) $AH - Im(f) = (Im(f_0), Im(f_0)I_1, Im(f_1)I_2) = (Z_6, Z_6I_1, \{0,2,4\}I_2)$.

Theorem 3.24:

Let G be any group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group,

be any two AH-subgroups of $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n), N_n(K) = (K_0, K_1I_1, \dots, K_nI_n); H_i, K_i \leq G$ $N_n(G)$. We have:

(a) $N_n(H) \cap N_n(K)$ is an AH-subgroup of $N_n(G)$.

(b) If $N_n(H), N_n(K)$ are AH-normal, then $N_n(H) \cdot N_n(K)$ is AH-normal.

(c) $N_n(H) \times N_n(K)$ is an AH-subgroup of $N_n(G) \times N_n(G)$.

(d) If $N_n(H), N_n(K)$ are AH-abelian, then $N_n(H) \cap N_n(K), N_n(G) \times N_n(G)$ are AH-abelian.

(e) If $N_n(H), N_n(K)$ are AH-cyclic, then $N_n(H) \cap N_n(K)$ is AH-cyclic.

(f) If $N_n(H), N_n(K)$ are AH-nilpotent, then $N_n(H) \cap N_n(K), N_n(G) \times N_n(G)$ are AH-nilpotent.

(g) If $N_n(H), N_n(K)$ are AH-solvable, then $N_n(H) \cdot N_n(K), N_n(G) \times N_n(G), N_n(G) \cap N_n(G)$ are AH-solvable.

(h) If $N_n(H), N_n(K)$ are AH- meta abelian, then $N_n(H) \cap N_n(K), N_n(G) \times N_n(G)$ are AH-meta abelian.

Proof:

It is well known from the classical group theoretical properties that $H_i \cap K_i$ is a subgroup of G , $H_i \times K_i$ is a subgroup of $G \times G$, and $H_i \cdot K_i$ is a subgroup of G under the assumption of normality of H_i, K_i , thus (a),(b),(c) are true.

Also, the direct product and the intersection of any two abelian, nilpotent, or solvable subgroups is the same, thus

(d),(f),(g) are true.

(h), (e) hold by the same argument.

Theorem 3.25:

Let G, K be any two groups, $N_n(G), N_n(K)$ be their corresponding n -refined neutrosophic groups,

be an AH-subgroup, $f_i: G \rightarrow K; 0 \leq i \leq n$ be a classical $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n); H_i \leq G$ homomorphism for all $i, f: N_n(G) \rightarrow N_n(K); f(a_0, a_1I_1, \dots, a_nI_n) = (f_0(a_0), f_1(a_1)I_1, \dots, f_n(a_n)I_n)$ be an AH-homomorphism, we have:

- (a) If $N_n(H)$ is AH-cyclic/AH-abelian, then $f(N_n(H))$ is AH-cyclic/AH-abelian.
- (b) If $N_n(H)$ is AH-nilpotent/AH-solvable, then $f(N_n(H))$ is AH-nilpotent/AH-solvable.
- (c) If $N_n(H)$ is AH-meta abelian, then $f(N_n(H))$ is AH-meta abelian.
- (d) If $N_n(H)$ is AH-normal, then $f(N_n(H))$ is AH-normal.
- (e) $AH-Ker(f)$ is an AH-normal subgroup of $N_n(G)$.
- (f) $AH-Im(f)$ is an AHS-subgroup of $N_n(K)$.

Proof:

(a),(b),(c),(d) It is well known that the homomorphic image of cyclic, abelian, nilpotent, normal, or meta abelian subgroup is the same, so the proof is complete.

(e) Since $Ker(f_i)$ is a normal subgroup of G for all $i, AH - Ker(f) = (Ker(f_0), Ker(f_1)I_1, \dots, Ker(f_n)I_n)$ as an AH-normal subgroup.

(f) The proof is similar to (e).

Theorem 3.26:

Let G be any finite group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n -refined neutrosophic group,

be any AH-subgroup. Then $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n)$

- (a) $O(N_n(H)) = O(H_0) \times O(H_1) \times \dots \times O(H_n)$.
- (b) Lagrange's theorem is true for AH-subgroups, i.e $O(N_n(H))$ divides $O(N_n(G))$.

Proof:

(a) Since $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n) = (h_0, h_1I_1, \dots, h_nI_n); h_i \in H_i$, we get $O(N_n(H)) = O(H_0) \times O(H_1) \times \dots \times O(H_n)$.

(b) Since $O(H_i)$ is a divisor of $O(G) = m$, then $O(N_n(H)) = O(H_0) \times O(H_1) \times \dots \times O(H_n)$ is a divisor of

. See [1]. $O(N_n(G)) = m^{n+1}$

Definition 3.27:

Let $(G, +)$ be any additive abelian group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group, is defined to be the set of all AH-homomorphisms between $N_n(G)$ and itself. $AH - End(N_n(G))$ is defined to be the set of all AHS-homomorphisms between $N_n(G)$ and itself. $AHS - End(N_n(G))$

Definition 3.28:

Let G be any group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group,

be an AH-subgroup of $N_n(G)$. We call $N_n(H)$ an AH-p $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n)$; $H_i \leq G$ subgroup if H_i is a p-group for all i .

Clearly, if G is a finite group, then $O(N_n(H))$ is a prime power according to Theorem 3.10.

Definition 3.29:

Let G be any group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group,

be an AH-subgroup of $N_n(G)$. The AH-derived subgroup of H $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n)$; $H_i \leq G$ can be defined as $[N_n(H)]' = (H'_0, H'_1I_1, \dots, H'_nI_n)$; $H'_i = \langle x^{-1}y^{-1}xy; \forall x, y \in H_i \rangle$.

Theorem 3.30:

Let G be any group, $N_n(G)$ be its corresponding n-refined neutrosophic group,

If $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n)$; $H_i \leq G$ be any AH-subgroup of $N_n(G)$. Then its AH-derived subgroup is trivial if and only if it is an AH-abelian subgroup.

Proof:

Suppose that $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n)$ is AH-abelian, hence H_i is abelian for all i . This implies that H'_i is trivial, thus $[N_n(H)]' = (H'_0, H'_1I_1, \dots, H'_nI_n)$ is trivial.

Conversely, If $[N_n(H)]' = (H'_0, H'_1I_1, \dots, H'_nI_n)$ is trivial, we find that H'_i is trivial, thus H_i is an abelian subgroup of G , which means that $N_n(H) = (H_0, H_1I_1, \dots, H_nI_n)$ is AH-abelian.

Remark 3.31:

There is a well known criteria for solvability of any classical group G . This criteria suggests that any group G is solvable if and only if the normal series formed from derived subgroups (G', G'', \dots) reaches to the trivial subgroup $\{e\}$ after n-steps.

We can use this argument to determine if an AH-subgroup is AH-solvable or not by computing AH-derivatives

$([N_n(H)]', [N_n(H)]'', \dots)$. If the previous series reaches to the trivial subgroup of $N_n(G)$, then $N_n(H)$ is an AH-solvable subgroup.

Also, any group G is meta abelian if and only if its derivative is an abelian subgroup. This idea can be generalized into AH-subgroups as follows:

Any AH-subgroup $N_n(H)$ is AH-meta abelian if and only if its AH-derivative subgroup is an AH-abelian.

References

- [1] Smarandache, F., " A Unifying Field in Logics: Neutrosophic Logic, Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Set, Neutrosophic Probability", American Research Press. Rehoboth, 2003.
- [2] Alhamido, R., and Gharibah, T., "Neutrosophic Crisp Tri-Topological Spaces", Journal of New Theory, Vol. 23 , pp.13-21. 2018.
- [3] Edalatpanah. S.A., "Systems of Neutrosophic Linear Equations", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 33, pp. 92-104. 2020.
- [4] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M., "Neutrosophic Linear Diophantine Equations With two Variables", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 38, pp. 22-30, 2020.
- [5] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M." n -Refined Neutrosophic Modules", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 36, pp. 1-11. 2020.
- [6] Alhamido, R., and Abobala, M., "AH-Substructures in Neutrosophic Modules", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 7, pp. 79-86 . 2020.
- [7] Abobala, M., "AH-Subspaces in Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 6 , pp. 80-86. 2020.
- [8] Abobala, M.,. "A Study of AH-Substructures in n -Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 9, pp.74-85. 2020.
- [9] Hatip, A., Alhamido, R., and Abobala, M., "A Contribution to Neutrosophic Groups", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 0, pp. 67-76 . 2019.
- [10] Abobala, M., " n -Refined Neutrosophic Groups I", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 0, pp. 27-34. 2020.
- [11] Kandasamy, V.W.B., and Smarandache, F., "Some Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures and Neutrosophic N-Algebraic Structures", Hexis, Phonex, Arizona, 2006.
- [12] Agboola, A.A.A., Akinola, A.D., and Oyebola, O.Y., " Neutrosophic Rings I" , International J.Mathcombin, Vol 4,pp 1-14. 2011
- [13] Agboola, A.A.A., "On Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Structures," Neutrosophic Sets and Systems,Vol.10, pp. 99-101. 2015.
- [14] Abobala, M., "Classical Homomorphisms Between Refined Neutrosophic Rings and Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5, pp. 72-75. 2020.
- [15] Smarandache, F., and Abobala, M., n -Refined neutrosophic Rings, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5 , pp. 83-90, 2020.
- [16] Kandasamy, I., Kandasamy, V., and Smarandache, F., "Algebraic structure of Neutrosophic Duplets in Neutrosophic Rings", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 18, pp. 85-95. 2018.
- [17] Yingcang, Ma., Xiaohong Zhang ., Smarandache, F., and Juanjuan, Z., "The Structure of Idempotents in Neutrosophic Rings and Neutrosophic Quadruple Rings", Symmetry Journal (MDPI), Vol. 11. 2019.
- [18] Kandasamy, V. W. B., Ilanthenral, K., and Smarandache, F., "Semi-Idempotents in Neutrosophic Rings", Mathematics Journal (MDPI), Vol. 7. 2019.

- [19] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Substructures of Neutrosophic Rings and Their Properties, International Journal of Neutrosophic Science", Vol. 4 , pp. 72-81, 2020.
- [20] Smarandache, F., " An Introduction To neutrosophic Genetics", International Journal of neutrosophic Science, Vol.13, 2021.
- [21] Martin, N, Smarandache, F, and Broumi, S., " Covid 19 Decision Making using Extended Plithogenic hypersoft Sets With Dual Dominant Attributes", International Journal of neutrosophic Science, Vol. 13, 2021.
- [22]Agboola, A.A., "Introduction To Neutro groups", International Journal of neutrosophic Science, Vol. 6, 2020.
- [23] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Substructures of Refined Neutrosophic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 5, pp. 59-66. 2020.
- [24] Smarandache, F., and Ali, M., "Neutrosophic Triplet Group", Neural. Compute. Appl. 2019.
- [25] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M., " AH-Homomorphisms In neutrosophic Rings and Refined Neutrosophic Rings", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 38, pp. 101-112, 2020.
- [26] Smarandache, F., and Kandasamy, V.W.B., " Finite Neutrosophic Complex Numbers", Source: arXiv. 2011.
- [27]. Suresh, R., and S. Palaniammal,. "Neutrosophic Weakly Generalized open and Closed Sets", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, Vol. 33, pp. 67-77,. 2020.
- [28] Sahin, M., Olgun, N., Uluçay, V., Kargin, A., and Smarandache, F. , "A New Similarity Measure Based on Falsity Value between Single Valued Neutrosophic Sets Based on the Centroid Points of Transformed Single Valued Neutrosophic Numbers with Applications to Pattern Recognition", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol. 15, pp. 31-48. 2017.
- [29] Ibrahim, M.A., Agboola, A.A.A, Badmus, B.S. and Akinleye, S.A., "On refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces I", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 7, pp. 97-109. 2020.
- [30] Ibrahim, M.A., Agboola, A.A.A, Badmus, B.S., and Akinleye, S.A., "On refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces II", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 9, pp. 22-36. 2020.
- [31] Abobala, M, " n -Cyclic Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Systems Of Sub-Indeterminacies, An Application To Rings and Modules", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol. 12, pp. 81-95 . 2020.
- [32] Smarandache, F., "Neutrosophic Set a Generalization of the Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets", Inter. J. Pure Appl. Math., pp. 287-297. 2005.
- [33] M. Ali, F. Smarandache, M. Shabir and L. Vladareanu., "Generalization of Neutrosophic Rings and Neutrosophic Fields", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol. 5, pp. 9-14, 2014.
- [34] Anuradha V. S., "Neutrosophic Fuzzy Hierarchical Clustering for Dengue Analysis in Sri Lanka", Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, vol. 31, pp. 179-199. 2020.
- [35] Olgun, N., and Hatip, A., "The Effect Of The Neutrosophic Logic On The Decision Making, in Quadruple Neutrosophic Theory And Applications", Belgium, EU, Pons Editions Brussels,pp. 238-253. 2020.
- [36] Zadeh, L. "Fuzzy Sets", Inform and Control, 8, pp.338-353. 1965.

- [37] Turksen, I., "Interval valued fuzzy sets based on normal forms", *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 20, pp.191-210, 1986. 1986.
- [38] Chalapathi, T., and Madhavi, L., "Neutrosophic Boolean Rings", *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 33, pp. 57-66. 2020.
- [39] Abobala, M., "Classical Homomorphisms Between n -refined Neutrosophic Rings", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*", Vol. 7, pp. 74-78. 2020.
- [40] Agboola, A.A.A., Akwu, A.D., and Oyebo, Y.T., " Neutrosophic Groups and Subgroups", *International .J .Math. Combin*, Vol. 3, pp. 1-9. 2012.
- [41] Smarandache, F., " n -Valued Refined Neutrosophic Logic and Its Applications in Physics", *Progress in Physics*, 143-146, Vol. 4, 2013.
- [42] Adeleke, E.O., Agboola, A.A.A.,and Smarandache, F., "Refined Neutrosophic Rings I", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 2(2), pp. 77-81. 2020.
- [43] Hatip, A., and Abobala, M., "AH-Substructures In Strong Refined Neutrosophic Modules", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 9, pp. 110-116 . 2020.
- [44] Hatip, A., and Olgun, N., "On Refined Neutrosophic R-Module", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 7, pp.87-96. 2020.
- [45] Chakraborty, A., Banik, B., Mondal, S.P., and Alam, S., "Arithmetic and Geometric Operators of Pentagonal Neutrosophic Number and its Application in Mobile Communication Service Based MCGDM Problem", *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, vol. 32, pp. 61-79. 2020.
- [46] Smarandache F., and Abobala, M., " n -Refined Neutrosophic Vector Spaces", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 7, pp. 47-54. 2020.
- [47] Sankari, H., and Abobala, M., "Solving Three Conjectures About Neutrosophic Quadruple Vector Spaces", *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 38, pp. 70-77. 2020.
- [48] Adeleke, E.O., Agboola, A.A.A., and Smarandache, F., "Refined Neutrosophic Rings II", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 2(2), pp. 89-94. 2020.
- [49] Abobala, M., On Refined Neutrosophic Matrices and Their Applications In Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations, *Journal Of Mathematics*, Hindawi, 2021
- [50] Abobala, M., A Study of Maximal and Minimal Ideals of n -Refined Neutrosophic Rings, *Journal of Fuzzy Extension and Applications*, Vol. 2, pp. 16-22, 2021.
- [51] Abobala, M., " Semi Homomorphisms and Algebraic Relations Between Strong Refined Neutrosophic Modules and Strong Neutrosophic Modules", *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 39, 2021.
- [52] Abobala, M., "On Some Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations", *Journal of New Theory*, Vol. 33, 2020.
- [53] Abobala, M., On The Representation of Neutrosophic Matrices by Neutrosophic Linear Transformations, *Journal of Mathematics*, Hindawi, 2021.
- [54] Abobala, M., "On Some Algebraic Properties of n -Refined Neutrosophic Elements and n -Refined Neutrosophic Linear Equations", *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, Hindawi, 2021

- [55] Kandasamy V, Smarandache F., and Kandasamy I., *Special Fuzzy Matrices for Social Scientists* . Printed in the United States of America, 2007, book, 99 pages.
- [56] Khaled, H., and Younus, A., and Mohammad, A., " The Rectangle Neutrosophic Fuzzy Matrices", Faculty of Education Journal Vol. 15, 2019. (Arabic version).
- [57] Abobala, M., *Partial Foundation of Neutrosophic Number Theory, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 39 , 2021.
- [58] F. Smarandache, *Neutrosophic Theory and Applications*, Le Quy Don Technical University, Faculty of Information technology, Hanoi, Vietnam, 17th May 2016.
- [59] Sankari, H, and Abobala, M., " On A New Criterion For The Solvability of non Simple Finite Groups and m-Abelian Solvability, *Journal of Mathematics*, Hindawi, 2021.
- [60] Giorgio, N, Mehmood, A., and Broumi, S., " Single Valued neutrosophic Filter", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 6, 2020.
- [61] Es, Haydar, A., "A Note On neutrosophic Soft Menger Topological Spaces", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol.7, 2020.
- [62] Abobala, M., Hatip, A., Olgun, N., Broumi, S., Salama, A,A., and Khaled, E, H., The algebraic creativity In The Neutrosophic Square Matrices, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 40, pp. 1-11, 2021.
- [63] Alhamido, K., R., "A New Approach of neutrosophic Topological Spaces", *International Journal of neutrosophic Science*, Vol.7, 2020.
- [64] Chellamani, P., and Ajay, D., "Pythagorean neutrosophic Fuzzy Graphs", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol. 11, 2021.
- [65] Abobala, M., "On Some Special Elements In Neutrosophic Rings and Refined Neutrosophic Rings", *Journal of New Theory*, vol. 33, 2020.
- [66] Milles, S, Barakat, M, and Latrech, A., " Completeness and Compactness In Standard Single Valued neutrosophic Metric Spaces", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, Vol.12 , 2021.
- [67] Agboola, A.A., "Introduction to Anti Groups", *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, vol.12, 2021.
- [68] Sankari, H, and Abobala, M, " A Contribution to m-Power Closed Groups", *UMM-Alqura University Journal for Applied Sciences*, KSA, 2020.